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orcid.org/0000-0003-3763-6347

S.V. Sytnik

K.D. Ushinsky South Ukrainian National
Pedagogical University, Odessa

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE STAGES OF INTERACTION

In the article the process of development of interpersonal interaction is explored. Selection and characterization of the main stages of this interaction. At the first contact is established between the actors of interaction, the second stage is disclosed through the joint activities of participants interpersonal interaction. The third stage is the completion of the interaction, with a positive result of which there is a mutual understanding between the participants of the interpersonal interaction. In case of failure to achieve the objectives of interaction possible options for further development of the situation - refusal of further interaction, change of purpose, or repeated attempt to achieve the goal of interpersonal interaction.

Key words: interpersonal interaction, compatible activity, congruence, communication, mutual understanding, stages of interpersonal interaction, subjects of interaction, mutual influence, communication, interpersonal relationship.

С.В. Ситнік

ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ЕТАПІВ МІЖСОБИСТІСНОЇ ВЗАЄМОДІЇ

У статті досліджено процес розвитку міжособистісної взаємодії. Виділенні та охарактеризовані основні етапи цієї взаємодії. На першому встановлюється контакт між суб'єктами взаємодії, другий етап розкривається через сумісну діяльність учасників міжособистісної взаємодії. Третій етап – це завершення взаємодії, при позитивному результаті якої спостерігається взаєморозуміння між учасниками міжособистісної взаємодії. У випадку недосягнення цілей взаємодії можливі такі варіанти подальшого розвитку ситуації – відмова від подальшої взаємодії, зміна мети, або повторна спроба досягнення мети міжособистісної взаємодії.

Ключові слова: міжособистісна взаємодія, сумісна діяльність, конгруенція, спілкування, взаєморозуміння, етапи міжособистісної взаємодії, суб'єкти взаємодії, взаємовплив, комунікація, міжособистісне взаємовідношення.

С.В.Сытник

ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ЭТАПОВ МЕЖЛИЧНОСТНОГО ВЗАИМОДЕЙСТВИЯ

В статье рассматривается процесс развития межличностного взаимодействия. Выделены и охарактеризованы основные этапы взаимодействия. На первом устанавливается контакт между субъектами взаимодействия, второй этап раскры-

вається через совместную деятельность участников межличностного взаимодействия. Третий этап – это завершение взаимодействия, при положительном результате которого наблюдается взаимопонимание между участниками межличностного взаимодействия. В случае не достижения целей межличностного взаимодействия возможны следующие варианты – отказ от взаимодействия; изменение цели; повторная попытка достижения цели взаимодействия.

Ключевые слова: межличностное взаимодействие, совместная деятельность, конгруэнция, общения, взаимопонимания, этапы межличностного взаимодействия, субъекты взаимодействия, взаимовлияние, коммуникация, межличностное взаимоотношение.

Introduction. Changes in social, economic and political life of the society put forward increased requirements for interpersonal interaction, which involves the organization of joint activity, adoption of managerial solutions in the professional sphere, establishment of business and interpersonal relationships in various social and professional groups. The problem of interpersonal interaction is actual in the theoretical and practical aspects that it is an important condition for solving social and psychological problems in various spheres of society. Interpersonal interaction was the object of research by well-known psychologists as B.G. Ananyev, V.S. Ageev, M. Andreeva, A.A. Bodalev, B.F. Lomov and others. These authors considered interpersonal interaction as an integral part of communication. Researchers M. Argyle, E. Berne and others, distinguished in the interpersonal interaction the phenomenon of "interaction", its structural components and mechanisms. The conditions and criteria for evaluating interpersonal interaction were studied by V.M. Kunicyna, N.V. Kazarionova, V.M. Pogolsha and others.

At the same time, theoretical aspects of interpersonal interaction demanding further studying that has caused the purpose of our research which consisted in studying of psychological features of stages of interpersonal interaction. Research problems: 1) to analyse special literature on a research problem; 2) to define the contents and the psychological characteristic of stages of interpersonal interaction.

In the framework of the first task of the study, it was clarified that the interaction acts as an "exchange of actions". In the concept of interaction between G. Mead and the stages of its development. In particular, the impulse, perception, manipulation, consummation (consumption). In these stages, the experience of the subjects of interaction is replenished, as well as the peculiar reorganization of the displacement of the value and semantic accents. Similar questions were studied by J. Szczepanski. In particular, the author noted that this

process that unfolds in time and space has certain stages of its development. Among them are: spatial contact, psychological contact in which the interest of subjects in this act of interaction is realized; social contact through joint activities. According to M. Argyle, the dynamics of interaction has three stages. This is physical contact, joint movement in space and compatible group action.

In the process of interaction V.N. Panferov highlighted five stages: perceptual, subject self-presentation, interdependence, information coordination and active compatibility. When interacting, an individual attitude is formed, which, according to V.F. Perevalov, passes through several stages. In particular, preparation for perception, perception, impression, understanding, fixation of attitude, preparation for the expression of a relationship. To study the stages of interpersonal interaction, it is important to consider the structure of this process. Thus, considering the structure of the interaction of B.F. Parigin, as its main components singled out cooperative activity, information connections, mutual influence, mutual relations and mutual understanding. Later this point of view was developed in the works of such psychologists as G.M. Andreeva, A.A. Bodalev, Ya.L. Kolominsky, B.F. Lomov. N.N. Obozov and others.

Understanding of the stages of interpersonal interaction is facilitated by consideration of the content component of this process. In particular, N. Hayes gives a content aspect with the help of such concepts as the context of social interaction, conversations and communication, interaction with others, interpersonal perception, attraction, attitudes, conflicts and cooperation. Something similar is found in the works of M. Argyle, which in interaction allocates verbal and nonverbal communication, eye contact, perception of others, dyad relations and social skills.

An important phenomenon in interpersonal interaction is the relationship, which was fundamentally examined by V.M. Myasischiv. The author notes that the system of attitudes towards people around and to oneself is the most specific characteristic of a person. In the relations of the individual, in his or her needs, interests, inclinations, it is not so much the product of certain abstract conditions, but primarily the result of how a person manages to interact with the environment, and how much space it gives for the development of individuality. This is observed in the objective activity and interaction with other people. In the views of V.M. Myasishchev, attitude is not only result of interaction of individuals, but also basis for emergence of the need of further interaction for them.

Considering the nature of interpersonal interaction, we note that the specific forms of interaction are interpersonal relationships and interpersonal communication (M.M. Obozov [6]). The interaction of people always implies their relationship to each other. The development of relations depends on the individuals themselves, on the conditions of the situation and the social system, on the subsequent transformation of contacts and the results of joint activities. The category of relations can be viewed on the one hand as a propensity to interact, and on the other hand as a really acting link within the framework of "subject-object", "subject-subject" (M. Obozov, 1980). So, psychological relations are present in subject-object and subject-subject relations. Interpersonal relations are always subject-subjective relations. In this sense the psychological relations act as a generic term to specific - interpersonal relations.

The essence of interaction consists not only in mutual exchange of actions but first of all, this is creation by people of mutual actions for implementation of joint activity (L.E. Orban-Lembrik [7]). Exploring the nature of the interaction M. Andreeva considers it as an organization of joint activity, while noting that it is inseparable from communication and at the same time they are not identical. The result of interpersonal interaction in the performance of joint activities is not only a practical result, but also the development of the psyche and consciousness of participants in interaction, improving interpersonal relationships (T.V. Senko, 2000). The interpersonal interaction in the studies of A.V. Gainullin. In particular, the author defines interpersonal interaction as a personal contact due to the space-time proximity of the subjects. A number of authors (V. Kozubovsky, V.V. Rubtsov) consider the reinforcement of motives for this interaction as an important condition for interpersonal interaction. In addition, to increase the reliability of interpersonal interaction, the distribution of forces and resources is important, which is conditioned by experience, knowledge, and skills of participants in the interaction.

The effectiveness of interaction depends on the individual characteristics of its participants. In particular, during the group decision of solving problems, the cognitive and emotional experiences of the partners of interpersonal interaction are summarized.

In the materials from interpersonal interaction, such concepts as mutual understanding, mutual influence, mutual relations, interpersonal communication, compatibility, exhaustion, etc. are widely used. Among these concepts, the most important, taking into account the process and the result of interaction is mutual understanding. This concept was studied by A.A. Bodalev, in particular,

the author noted that the ability to understand others refers to the socio-perceptual competence of the individual. At the same time, empathy and reflection contribute to this competence. The importance of mutual understanding is also related to the fact that interpersonal interaction begins with a person's perception of a person, that is, interpersonal cognition occurs. This process is influenced by the personality characteristics of the subjects of interaction. So, self-understanding and adequate self-esteem affect the process of cognition of other people (A.A. Bodalev [8]). In particular, subjects who are self-confident tend to evaluate other people as benevolent. Uncertain people often perceive others as unfriendly to them. Self-criticism allows you to perceive others more adequately. Authoritarian subjects of interaction in comparison with democratic express more rigid judgments concerning perception of the person. Persons with a complex psychic organization deeper and more accurately assess the partners in communication. Cognition in interaction is not a one-time act. In addition to cognition, feedback, communication and interaction take place.

There is connection between personal interaction and joint activity. At the same time, according to A.L. Zhuravlev, interaction is an important factor for the emergence and development of joint activities. At the same time, joint activities involve the interaction of its participants [4]. In general, the socio-psychological analysis of joint activities in the literature is presented fragmentarily. B.F. Lomov noted that psychology needs to create a theory of joint activity that would reveal its complex structure, dynamics, and ways of its development. As M. Andreeva notes, the general psychological theory of activity determines certain principles for socio-psychological research. A successful attempt to systematize the various studies of joint activities in labor collectives belongs to A.L. Zhuravlev. Therefore the problem of joint activity as forms of interpersonal interaction is relevant and perspective for development.

Discussion. The second task of the study was aimed at determining the stages of interpersonal interaction. On the basis of theoretical and methodological research it is shown that interpersonal interaction begins with the definition of goals and motives. The value of interaction motivation is to strengthen the relationship between participants in interpersonal interaction. For each of them, motive is another person, a partner in communication (M.I. Lisina, 1986). In the studies of B.F. Lomov it is indicated that there is an interference between the motives and goals in the interaction. In this connection, it is possible to elucidate the exciting aspects of interpersonal interaction. The psychological content of the exciting side of interaction is associated with a holistic-motivational

exchange. As B.F. Lomov noted, in the process of communication, there is a mutual exchange of ideas, interests, moods, feelings, attitudes, character traits, etc. Thanks to such an exchange, mutual correction of positions, goals, interests is carried out. That is, a motivational-objective interaction can be observed.

For the emergence of interpersonal interaction, there must be a steady excitation to the corresponding activity. Any activity of the individual begins with his need. This can be, for example, physical needs, security needs, communication, achievement of a certain status, etc. Further, when a subject meets a social object and believes that this object corresponds to his needs, then as a result, interest arises. Then the goal of interaction with this social object is determined. If the situation is favorable for interaction, then the motive is updated before it begins. In the future, there is an establishment of contact between the participants in the interaction. Primary contact begins with perception of appearance, features of activity and behavior of people. At the initial stage of interaction, contacts between people are somewhat simplistic, in the course of which they exchange information. From the initial contacts depends on the acceptance or not acceptance of partners by each other. These phenomena refer to the first, the initial stage of interpersonal interaction. At this stage an important role is played by the congruence effect, which turns out to confirm the role expectations of the interaction participants. The congruence effect is associated with the personality characteristics of subjects of interpersonal interaction. The congruence presupposes the emergence of trust, sympathy on the subconscious level. In addition, it enhances the partners' sense of complicity, interest, and exploratory mutual activity. The result of congruence and primary contacts is the establishment of feedback between people, represents a response that supports interaction, and also communicates to another person about how its behavior and actions are perceived (V.G. Krisko, 2006).

Prerequisites of achievement of congruence is experience of accessory, empathy, identification. At the first stage of interpersonal interaction, the regulation of communication is effected by the influence of the "one's self-concept" and image of representation of partners about each other. This stage is completed by the choice of joint actions, which makes it possible to begin joint activities, which is the second phase of interpersonal interaction. By coordinating their positions, the subjects of interaction enter into a "agreement-disagreement" relationship with each other. In case of agreement, joint activities appear, accompanied by the distribution of roles and functions among the participants in the interaction. In order for this distribution to be effective from

the participants in the interaction, tolerance, comprehensiveness, persistence and other moral and volitional qualities of the individual are required, based on the high level of his consciousness.

Interpersonal interactions at the second stage of the development gain signs of productive joint activity. The following forms of its organization are distinguished: each participant does the part of the general work independently of another. The general task is carried out consistently by each participant. There is a simultaneous interaction of each participant with all the others (V.G. Krisko, 2006). During joint activities, people's influence on each other is observed at the level of motivational, cognitive and emotional-volitional components of the individual. Interpersonal interaction is an external outline of a person's relationship to the people who surround him. The main components of interaction are motivational, cognitive and emotional-volitional. The motivational component concerns the motivational and objective aspect of interaction. The cognitive component is connected with such parties of interpersonal interaction as communicative, provides for mutual information; The perceptual side is revealed through mutual perception, mutual evaluation and mutual understanding; the emotional-strong-willed side concerns sympathy - antipathy, changes in each other's behavior.

The internal basis of the interpersonal relationship is a relationship involving the motivational (interest in another), communicative (trust in other), perceptual (the image of other), emotional-volitional (expectation of a certain behavior, emotional reactions to other) (A.I. Shipilov [10]). .

At the same time such the mechanism are used: suggestion, conformism, beliefs, identification, reflection, causal attribution, imitations, action compensation, attraction, empathy, polarization, reflection of emotions and others. These mechanisms contribute to the reconciliation of thoughts, feelings, relations of partners of joint activity. The effectiveness of this activity is also influenced by: psychological climate, motives of interaction, processes of mutual influence. The content of these psychological mechanisms is reveals as follows. Persuasion is an impact on the consciousness of the person for which the argumentation and logic are important. At the time of suggestion, there is a reduction in the criticality of the perception of information that is perceived, as well as a weakening of understanding, logical analysis and evaluation of this information. The effectiveness of suggestion is important non-verbal means of communication, the situation of interaction, the emotional state of the one who perceives suggestion. Conformism is the subordination of the personality to the

judgment of others. In this case, there is a certain pressure on such a person. In social psychology, this phenomenon is known as group pressure. Conformism is the mechanism of both the "personality-group" interaction and interpersonal interaction. Identification is used during interpersonal interaction for the cognition of other. At the same time the person in own imagination goes to the place of another and tries to perceive, understand, feel for that another. That is, the inner world of the other is learned by assimilating yourself to another. A person behaves the way it thinks another person can behave in this situation. This mechanism contributes to the development of cooperative and competitive interaction.

The next psychological mechanism of interpersonal interaction is imitation. It involves imitating one or another example or pattern of various behavioral manifestations. Empathy as a psychological mechanism is manifested in sympathy for another. The attraction is connected with the formation of a stable, positive feeling for another. Mirroring emotions as a psychological mechanism is manifested in the process of exchange of unimodal emotional reactions. That is, reflection of the emotional state of another. The mechanism of polarization of emotions strengthens the opposite on modality emotional conditions of the opponent.

With positive development, interpersonal interaction reaches the third stage, which is characterized by the emergence of mutual understanding between the participants in the interaction. Mutual understanding of people involves understanding the actions of the partner, and it also contributes to the achievement of the goal in joint activities. Also, the characteristics of mutual understanding are:

a) adequacy – accuracy of the mental reflection of the individual, which is perceived;

b) identification – assimilation by the individual of the personality with the identity of other individual.

Mutual understanding at interaction can be considered from two sides: as reflection in consciousness of interacting subjects – purposes, motives, emotions, attitudes towards each other; and as the acceptance of these goals, allowing to establish relationships. The main mechanisms of mutual understanding are: identification, empathy and reflection (V.O. Sosnin). At the same time, identification is considered as process of assimilation of oneself to another person, the process of identification with another person. When interacting, identification is directed toward cognition, understanding thoughts and ideas differ-

ently. Identification by its content is close to empathy. So, empathy is the thought process of assimilation ourselves to another person, but with the purpose of understanding, in the affective way, experiences of feelings of another person.

During the understanding of each other there is reflection. That is, an individual's awareness of how he is perceived by the partner in interaction. The reflection acts as a peculiar feedback which promotes formation of strategy of behavior of subjects of interaction.

The third stage of interpersonal interaction is related to the implementation of the task of joint activity. Interpersonal interaction can be constructive or conflictual. In the first case, there are phenomena such as mutual understanding, cohesion, coherence, exhaustion, joint activities, development of relationships, and others. In the second case, there are clashes of opinions and points of view, inadequate perception of the situation and participants in the interaction. Joint activities based on interpersonal interaction can have three variants of its completion in accordance with the stated goal of the activity. Firstly, the achievement of the goal of interpersonal interaction, which is combined with the emergence of mutual understanding between the participants in the interaction. Secondly, failure to achieve the goal and possible refusal of participants from it. Thirdly, return to the beginning of the interaction for a second attempt to achieve its goal.

Thus, the first stage in the development of interpersonal interaction is connected with the beginning of the interaction, the second with joint activity, the third with the result of interaction.

Conclusions and prospects for further research.

1. The development of interpersonal interaction occurs in three stages. At the first stage after the emergence of interest, purpose and directly the motive of interaction, psychological contact is established between its participants. At this stage, the congruence effect is important. At the second stage: there is a joint activity aimed at achieving the goal of interpersonal interaction. At the third stage, the interaction is completed in connection with the obtaining of its result.

2. The completion of interpersonal interaction and joint activities is related to the fulfillment of the task of this activity. The following options of completion of this process are possible: firstly, the achievement of the goal of interpersonal interaction and joint activities; secondly, the rejection of further interaction, or a change of the purpose; thirdly, a second attempt to achieve the goal of

interpersonal interaction. A positive result is accompanied with the emergence of mutual understanding between the participants of the interaction.

Further researches on this subject are associated with creation of model of interpersonal interaction which considers system connections between psychological phenomena which are observed in this process.

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